

EARTH SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE KINEMATIC PARAMETERS OF THE SHARUR UPLIFT FROM PALEOMAGNETIC DATA (LESSER CAUCASUS, AZERBAIJAN, NAKHCHIVAN)

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of studies of the Jurassic formations of the sections of Nakhchivan (Azerbaijan) in order to solve the problem of horizontal movements. Jurassic formations have been studied from Nehrem section. The conducted paleomagnetic studies have shown that the identified paleomagnetic directions are ancient, synchronous with the time of the Jurassic formations and can be used to analyze patterns associated with the ancient magnetic field, as well as for paleotectonic reconstructions of the region.

Keywords: magnetization, magnetic susceptibility, horizontal displacements, kinematic parameters, tectonics, stratigraphy, lithology.

INTRODUCTION The paleomagnetic method is quite successfully used in the study of volcanogenic rocks. Rocks of this type serve as a favorable object for paleomagnetic studies. In most cases, volcanogenic rocks have a large and fairly stable natural remanent magnetization.

The assumption that volcanic rocks acquire magnetization, corresponding to the epoch of the action of the geomagnetic field in a given place, is the physical basis for studying the behavior of the geomagnetic field.

The most complete section of the Jurassic deposits has been studied in the area of the Negram railway station, along the left tributary of the Negramchay. Here the Jurassic deposits are exposed as a strip stretching almost in the latitudinal direction. The section shows all three divisions of the Jurassic, richly characterized faunistically, with the exception of the Liassic, expressed by effusive rocks.

This paper presents the results of paleomagnetic studies of Jurassic rocks selected from the Negram section located on the territory of Nakhchivan. Magneto-mineralogical studies were carried out in the laboratory of the Institute of Geology and Geophysics according to the method generally accepted in paleomagnetism. When studying the magnetic properties and diagnostics of ferromagnetic minerals, we were guided by the works of T. Nagata, D.M. Pechersky, S.Yu. Brodskaya, V.E. Pavlov and others [1]

METHOD. For confident paleomagnetic constructions, it is necessary to establish the nature of the natural remanent magnetization J_n^0 and determine the ferromagnetic minerals responsible for J_n . For this purpose, non-heating methods of magnetic cleaning were used. These are: a) a method of demagnetization of natural residual magnetization in an alternating magnetic field; b) magnetic cleaning method; and c) reprecipitation method. Thermomagnetic studies were carried out, including: taking the temperature demagnetization curves I_{rs} and determining the Curie points. Measurements of the magnitude and direction of the natural remanent magnetization were carried out on a JR-6 two-speed spin magnetometer. The value of the magnetic susceptibility was measured by a Czech device KT-5.

The Negram section is represented by the Callovian, Aalenian, Bajocian, and Bathonian stages of the Jurassic period. From the studied section, 50 bulk samples were collected, from which 150 cubes 24x24 mm in size were cut. The total thickness of the Negram section is 252 m. The entire collection of samples was measured in the laboratory according to the standard method adopted in paleomagnetism.

THE DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS.

Stereograms for the studied Jurassic formations were built (Ftg/1).

Fig.1. In distributions of Jurassic rocks of the Negram section (a - before magnetic cleaning; b - after magnetic cleaning).

According to paleomagnetic data, it was found that in the Jurassic, the Negram section was at paleolatitude 24° and moved north to 1400 ± 48 km. The rate of translational movement of the Negram block is 2.1-2.2

cm/year. The Negram block rotated correspondingly clockwise by 21° .

As a result of the studies carried out in the Negram section, 7 zones were established - 4 of direct polarity and 3 zones of reverse polarity. (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Regional scheme of magnetostratigraphic sections of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic: 1-zone of reverse magnetization; 2-zone of direct magnetization 3-lines of correlation I - consolidated scale of the Mesozoic of Azerbaijan; II - the general scale of Russia .;

We also determined the average directions of magnetization and coordinates of the paleomagnetic pole of the region under study. In most cases, the viscous magnetization did not exceed 40% J_n . All samples were subjected to stepwise cleaning (with a step of 2×10^2 A/m) by an alternating magnetic field up to 4×10^4 A/m. According to paleomagnetic data, it was established that in the Jurassic Negram section was located at a paleolatitude of 24° , moved to the north by 1400 ± 30 km, the rate of translational movements was 2.1-2,2 cm/year. Tectonik Block Negram turned correspondingly clockwise by 21° .

The results of laboratory studies indicate the primacy of the nature of natural residual magnetization and the correspondence of its direction to the paleotime of formation of the studied rocks. Also, the average directions of magnetization and the coordinates of

the paleomagnetic pole of the studied region $D=21^{\circ}$, $J=40^{\circ}$ were determined. $K=9$, $\alpha_{95}=8$, $\Phi=68$, $\Lambda=246^{\circ}$.

CONCLUSION

For the first time in Nakhchivan, on the basis of paleomagnetic data, turns were studied and the kinematic parameters of the movement of crustal blocks were determined: clockwise turns and horizontal movements to the north.

Thus, the conducted paleomagnetic studies have shown that the identified paleomagnetic directions are ancient, synchronous with the time of rock formation and can be used to analyze patterns associated with the ancient magnetic field, as well as paleostratigraphic reconstructions of the region.

Referenses

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